

ISic2953

I.Sicily inscription 2953

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Morgantina

Place of origin (modern)

Morgantina

Provenance

Contr. San Francesco

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Aidone, Museo Archeologico di
Aidone

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645318

EDCS 70900971

Bibliography

Fiorentini, G. 1980-1981. Ricerche archeologiche nella Sicilia centro-meridionale. *Kokalos*. 26-27: 581-600. At 598 tav.85

Antonaccio, C. M. 1999. An inscribed stele from archaic Morgantina. *Kadmos*. 38: 87-96. At 88 n.3

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